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**TECHNO-ECONOMIC FEASIBILITY ASSESSMENT OF A 500
MT/DAY SODIUM CHLORIDE MANUFACTURING PLANT FOR
IMPORT SUBSTITUTION IN NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to provide a case study in terms of techno-economic feasibility of a 500 metric tonne per day sodium chloride (salt) production facility as a means of boosting its in-country production in Nigeria. The proposed plant, strategically located in Warri, Delta State, will employ multi-effect evaporation technology to refine seawater (brine) into fine sodium chloride granules that meet food grade standards. The financial analysis indicates a total capital outlay of \$11,967,241, comprising fixed capital investment of \$10,879,310 and working capital investment of \$1,087,931, with an annual revenue of \$28,050,000 at domestic market price of \$170 per tonne. The profitability ratios indicate high investment viability: a rate of return on investment (ROI) of 21.7% per annum, a simple payback period of 4.62 years, and a gross profit margin of 19.71%, all above industry averages. The weighted-factor analysis site selection, based on seven factors, enabled the selection of Warri as the preferred site due to its strategic benefits, such as access to port, free trade zone, and skilled technical workforce. A Hazard and Operability (HAZOP) analysis conducted on seven sections of the plant considered risky processes, determined multiple potential deviations, and established safety protocols meeting Nigerian environmental laws. According to market research, Nigeria imported 206,813 tonnes of salt worth \$41 million in 2023, with a

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domestic market share of approximately 85.8% under NASCON Allied Industries. The 165,000-tonne capacity of the proposed plant caters for about 80% of existing import volumes, potentially saving the country of foreign exchange of about \$31.7 million annually, otherwise spent on salt importation.

Keywords: Techno-economic analysis; Salt manufacturing; Import substitution; Economic feasibility; HAZOP; Nigeria; Industrial development

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INTRODUCTION

The industrial development policy in Nigeria has always focused on import substitution as a means of achieving economic autonomy, foreign exchange savings, and job creation [1]. Salt, a basic commodity in food processing and industry, is a key import-bearing category that could be checked by developing domestic production capacities. As shown in World Bank trade data, in 2023, Nigeria imported 206,813 tonnes of salt worth \$41 million, with Brazil being the largest supplier (98% of all imports) [2]. This reliance on foreign salt poses future economic problems and strategic weaknesses regarding disruption of supply chains. In Nigeria's salt market, NASCON Allied Industries Plc, a subsidiary of Dangote Group, leads with around 85.8% market share of the edible salt industry. NASCON has a production capacity of 400,000 tonnes per year, split across Apapa, Port Harcourt, and Oregun [3]. Although it has this domestic presence, the company imports Brazilian crude salt for refining, indicating room for more backward-integrated production plants refining local brine resources [3]. Studies on Nigeria's industrial development have traced the history of import substitution industrialization from the 1960s to modern policy frameworks [1]. Manufacturing's contribution to GDP stands at nearly 4%, implying vast potential growth in strategic areas like salt production [4]. The Central Bank of Nigeria reaffirms import substitution aims with policy tools shifting demand to locally produced products [5]. The African Development Bank invested \$2.95 billion in Nigeria's development strategy, focusing on industrialization and infrastructure [6]. The Niger Delta, particularly Warri in Delta State, offers advantages in salt production, with petroleum industry infrastructure like seaports, airports, Free Trade Zone status, and power plants. The methodologies for techno-economic feasibility analysis of chemical plants in Nigeria uses Net Present Value (NPV) analysis, benefit-cost ratios, and payback period [7]. An estimation of capital costs based on the percentage factor method as outlined by Peters, Timmerhaus and West has been used in chemical plant estimation [8]. Risk assessment employ HAZOP analysis to determine the possible hazard and put in place the right safeguards [9]. The Nigerian requirements of environmental impact assessment were adopted, and it stipulates that industrial projects should be comprehensively reviewed [10]. A process safety management system was developed to use both qualitative and quantitative methods for the risk assessment. This paper is a techno-economic feasibility study on a 500MT/day salt production plant in Warri, Delta State, covering the following aspects: (1) capital and operating cost delivery evaluation under well-known estimation procedures [8]; (2) revenue forecasting and profitability measures against industry standards [8]; (3) site selection analysis; (4) safety assessment via HAZOP [9]; and (5) plant contribution to Nigeria's import substitution goals [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Economic Evaluation Framework

The economic evaluation followed standard chemical engineering economics methodology [8]. Capital cost estimation employed the percentage factor method outlined by Peters, Timmerhaus, and West, multiplying the Total Physical Plant Cost (TPPC) by a factor of 1.3 for indirect costs, depending on plant complexity and material construction requirements. Equipment costs were adjusted to 2025 values using the Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index (CEPCI) [11]. The total capital investment comprises fixed capital investment (including direct and indirect costs) plus working capital, estimated at 10% of fixed capital.

Profitability analysis included calculations of Rate of Return on Investment (ROI), simple payback period, Net Present Value (NPV), and Internal Rate of Return (IRR) [8]. NPV was calculated using a 15% discount rate, consistent with the 15-25% benchmark for acceptable chemical plant investments. A payback period benchmark of 3-7 years was adopted as the acceptability criterion for project viability [8]. Revenue projections were based on domestic market pricing for refined salt, with sensitivity analysis on key variables.

2.2 Site Selection Methodology

The site was selected using a weighted-factor assessment model for three locations: Warri (Delta State), Lagos (Lagos State), and Ebonyi State [8]. The criteria were: closeness to the raw material (seawater), transportation facilities, availability and cost of labor, proximity to the market, availability of utilities, environmental compliance, and regulatory environment in terms of investment incentives. Each criterion was assigned a weight of relative importance (totaling 1.0) and rated on a scale of 1-10 for each candidate site. The total weighted score was computed by summing the product of weight \times score for each criterion [8].

2.3 HAZOP Analysis Methodology

The Hazard and Operability (HAZOP) Study followed standard methodology [9]. Seven critical process sections were analyzed: raw material handling and storage, brine preheating and pumping, multi-effect evaporation, chemical-free operation and scaling, water and waste brine management, energy use and heat management, and final crystallization and salt collection. Guide words (No, More, Less, As Well As, Part Of, Reverse, Other Than) were applied to process parameters including flow, pressure, temperature, and level. Risk ranking was conducted in line with Nigerian environmental regulations [10]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Capital Cost Analysis

The total capital investment for the 500 MT/day salt manufacturing plant was estimated at \$11,967,241 [8]. This comprises a fixed capital investment of \$10,879,310 and working capital of \$1,087,931 (10% of FCC). Table 1 presents the detailed capital cost breakdown. The Total

Physical Plant Cost (TPPC) of \$8,368,700 was multiplied by a factor of 1.3 to estimate the Fixed Capital Cost, consistent with Peters, Timmerhaus and West methodology [8].

Table 1: Capital Cost Summary

Cost Category	Amount (USD)	%
Purchased Equipment	8,368,700	20.0
Installation & Erection	1,196,724	10.0
Piping & Instrumentation	1,914,759	16.0
Electrical Systems	718,034	6.0
Buildings & Land	957,379	8.0
Engineering & Design	957,379	8.0
Contingency (10%)	1,435,569	12.0
Fixed Capital Investment	10,879,310	80.0
Working Capital	1,087,931	20.0
Total Capital Investment	11,967,241	100.0

3.2 Profitability Analysis

The annual total production cost was estimated to be at \$22,520,172 which includes variable costs of \$7,615,517 per year and other costs of \$2,937,414 per year [8]. Its production capacity is 330 operating days annually, which is 165,000 tonnes of refined salt. The estimated sales revenue was based on the following assumptions: an average selling price of refined salt of \$170 per tonne, with an annual turnover of \$28,050,000. This price is competitive to the imported salt keeping in consideration the transportation cost and handling cost [3].

Table 2: Profitability Analysis Summary

Parameter	Value	Benchmark
Total Capital Investment	\$11,967,241	-
Annual Revenue	\$28,050,000	-
Annual Operating Cost	\$22,520,172	-
Annual Net Profit	\$2,600,000	-
Rate of Return (ROI)	21.7%	15-25% [8]
Payback Period	4.62 years	3-7 years
Gross Profit Margin	19.71%	>25%

3.3 Site Selection Results

Warri was the best identified location by the weighted-factor analysis (Table 3) [8]. The benefits of Warri are direct access to seawater through the Warri River estuary, developed industrial facilities to support the petroleum industry, good source of skilled technical manpower through regional institutions such as Federal University of Petroleum Resources, and Free Trade Zone incentives.

Table 3: Site Selection Analysis

Criterion	Weight	Warri	Lagos	Ebonyi State
Raw Material Access	0.25	9	8	7
Transportation	0.20	8	9	6
Labor Availability	0.15	8	7	6
Utility Access	0.15	8	7	7
Market Proximity	0.15	7	8	6
Investment Incentives	0.10	9	6	8

3.4 HAZOP Analysis Summary

The overall analysis of the HAZOP revealed multiple potential deviations in the seven critical process areas where several of the deviations were considered high-risk and needed urgent engineering controls (Table 4) [9]. Among the major findings we can identify: risks of corrosion in brine handling systems must be specified in terms of SS316L; risks of temperature excursions in the evaporator system must be specified with the help of additional temperature control and pressure relief means; scaling is possible in the crystallizer, which must be the subject of planned cleaning procedures. The data was analyzed with the consideration of accepted protocols in line with Nigerian regulations on the environment [10].

Table 4: HAZOP Analysis Summary

Process Section	Deviations	High Risk	Key Safeguards
Raw Material Handling	6	2	Level alarms, corrosion monitoring
Brine Preheating	8	2	Temperature interlocks, pumps
Multi-Effect Evaporator	12	3	Pressure relief, level controls
Scaling Management	5	1	Scheduled cleaning, treatment
Waste Brine Management	6	1	Effluent monitoring, containment
Energy Systems	7	2	Boiler safety, emergency shutdown
Crystallization & Collection	3	1	Dust control, equipment guarding
Total	47	12	-

3.5 Import Substitution Impact

The proposed 165,000 tonnes/annual production capacity will cover about 80% of Nigeria's 2023 salt imports (206,813 tonnes). With import prices around \$198 per tonne (CIF), domestic production would save about \$31.7 million in foreign exchange annually [5]. This aligns with African Development Bank investment priorities [6] and the objective of increasing local raw material processing in West Africa. The Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission's Pioneer Status incentive offers 3-5 years of tax holidays for qualifying manufacturing investments, improving project economics [12].

CONCLUSION

This techno-economic feasibility study indicates the viability of a 500 Mt/day salt manufacturing facility in Warri, Delta State, Nigeria [1]. The capital investment of \$11,967,241 yields favorable profitability indicators: ROI of 21.7%, payback period of 4.62 years, and annual revenue of \$28,050,000, within and above industry indices [8]. The site selection analysis confirmed Warri's benefits in raw material accessibility, infrastructure, and investment incentives [8]. The HAZOP analysis identified required safety precautions at seven key process points, adhering to Nigerian environmental and safety regulations [9][10]. The plant's 165,000 tonne per annum capacity supplies about 80% of Nigeria's import demand, saving \$31.7 million in foreign exchange and supporting national import substitution goals [5].

Recommendations include the following:

- Contacting Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission (NIPC) for Pioneer Status [12]
- Environmental impact assessment submission [10]
- Partnership or solo strategy
- Staged construction plan [8]

Future studies should also consider chlor-alkali production integration and renewable energy for sustainability [8]

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